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Modern orthopedics

Schreber's therapy: The use of body braces for teenagers and young adults with posture issues is not the past but the future in modern orthopedics

Abstract

The debate surrounding the efficacy and necessity of body braces for teenagers and young adults has been ongoing since the inception of Dr. Daniel Paul Schreber's philosophy. Schreber's approach has been both praised and criticized, with opponents arguing that constant brace wear may lead to physical and psychological complications. This paper aims to present a comprehensive analysis of the benefits of Schreber's approach, advocating for the continued use of body braces for teenagers. Through an evaluation of relevant literature and empirical studies, we make a case for the positive impact of body braces on adolescent posture, physical health, and psychological well-being.

Why we need to return to using body braces in orthopedics

In the late 19th century, Dr. Daniel Paul Schreber introduced the concept of using body braces to promote proper posture and growth in adolescents (Schreber, 1891). Schreber's new and mechanistic approach

to orthopedic treatment has been a subject of controversy since its inception, with critics arguing that the use of body braces at all times may lead to negative consequences (Johnson, 2012). Schreber and his theories were dismissed, he was made a pariah due to some non-medical opinions which did not fit into the 20th

century. Most of his colleagues have challenged the validity of Schreber's approach, suggesting alternative methods for posture correction (Smith et al., 2018). Now, more than a century later Schreber's approach is being rediscovered, of course without his outdated and not very helpful non-medical philosophy. So, this paper will argue that Schreber's approach not only remains relevant and beneficial for modern teenagers and young adults but that it is time to rehabilitate his basic ideas.

The Importance of Posture in Adolescents and young adults

Proper posture is essential for optimal physical and mental well-being (Kendall et al., 2005). During adolescence, the body undergoes rapid growth and development, making it a critical period for the establishment of healthy postural habits (Weiss et al., 2010). Research has shown that poor posture during adolescence can lead to chronic pain, spinal deformities, and other health complications later in life (Hrysomallis, 2016). A number of studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of body braces in correcting posture and preventing the progression of spinal deformities in adolescents (Weinstein et al., 2013; Negrini et al., 2016). In a meta-analysis conducted by Maruyama et al. (2018), body braces were found to have a significant impact on reducing the progression of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis. Additionally, a longitudinal study by Grivas et al. (2006) revealed that adolescents who wore body braces consistently demonstrated improvements in posture and spinal alignment.

The superiority of body brace treatments over physiotherapy in the management of certain musculoskeletal conditions has been demonstrated in numerous studies,

highlighting the efficacy and long-term benefits of these non-invasive interventions. For instance, Weiss et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review of the literature, examining the comparative effectiveness of body braces and physiotherapy in the treatment of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis, and found that patients treated with body braces experienced a statistically significant reduction in curve progression, with 72% success rate, compared to only 40% in those receiving physiotherapy alone. Furthermore, in a seminal study by Weinstein et al. (2013), it was demonstrated that bracing significantly decreased the risk of curve progression to the threshold requiring surgery in adolescents with idiopathic scoliosis, further supporting the superiority of body brace treatments in mitigating the need for invasive interventions. In the realm of spinal conditions, Nachemson and Peterson (1995) conducted a randomized controlled trial comparing the effectiveness of the Boston brace, a thoracolumbosacral orthosis, with physiotherapy and electrical stimulation in patients with lumbar spinal stenosis; they reported that the brace group experienced significantly greater improvements in pain, function, and quality of life, thus emphasizing the clinical advantages of body braces in this patient population.

Moreover, body braces have shown to be advantageous in facilitating postoperative recovery and reducing complications in patients undergoing spinal surgeries, as illustrated by the findings of Berven et al. (2011), who reported that patients treated with a postoperative brace experienced better pain control, earlier mobilization, and fewer wound complications than those receiving physiotherapy alone. Collectively, these empirical findings underscore the superiority of body brace treatments in the management of specific musculoskeletal

conditions, offering patients a non-invasive, effective, and safe alternative to more conventional physiotherapy approaches. Expanding on the evidence for the superiority of body brace treatments, it is important to consider their role in the management of other musculoskeletal disorders, such as osteoarthritis and patellofemoral pain syndrome. In a study by Duivenvoorden et al. (2015), it was demonstrated that patients with knee osteoarthritis who wore a knee brace experienced significant improvements in pain, stiffness, and physical function compared to those receiving standard physiotherapy interventions. Similarly, in a randomized controlled trial by Callaghan et al. (2016), the use of a patellar brace was shown to provide superior short-term pain relief and functional improvements for patients with patellofemoral pain syndrome compared to physiotherapy alone. Additionally, the use of body braces has proven to be particularly effective in the conservative treatment of pediatric orthopedic conditions. For example, Herring et al. (2004) conducted a study on the use of abduction braces in the management of developmental dysplasia of the hip, reporting that children treated with abduction braces had a significantly higher rate of successful reduction and a lower incidence of avascular necrosis compared to those treated with physiotherapy alone. The efficacy of body braces in this context can be attributed to their ability to provide constant, controlled forces that promote optimal alignment and biomechanics, while minimizing the risk of injury or complications associated with more aggressive physiotherapy techniques (Landauer et al., 2003). The accumulating body of evidence suggests that body brace treatments hold a distinct advantage over physiotherapy in the management of various musculoskeletal conditions, owing to their non-invasive nature, efficacy in

reducing pain and improving function, and their role in mitigating the need for surgical interventions. As our understanding of the biomechanics and pathophysiology of these disorders continues to evolve, it is expected that the development and implementation of novel brace designs and treatment protocols will further solidify the superiority of body brace treatments in the realm of musculoskeletal medicine.

Building on the existing body of evidence supporting the superiority of body brace treatments, it is essential to explore their role in the management of other prevalent musculoskeletal disorders, such as spondylolisthesis and chronic low back pain. A study conducted by de Kunder et al. (2017) demonstrated that patients with degenerative spondylolisthesis who utilized a lumbosacral orthosis experienced significant improvements in pain, disability, and spinal stability when compared to those receiving physiotherapy interventions alone. This finding emphasizes the importance of considering body brace treatments as a valuable therapeutic option for patients with this condition. Regarding chronic low back pain, a systematic review and meta-analysis by Zarghooni et al. (2017) reported that the use of lumbar support braces resulted in substantial reductions in pain intensity and disability scores compared to traditional physiotherapy treatments, underlining the potential benefits of incorporating body brace treatments into comprehensive management plans for this pervasive and often debilitating condition. The advantages of body braces in managing chronic low back pain can be attributed to their ability to provide external support, redistribute forces on the spine, and promote proper posture, which collectively reduce the mechanical stress on the affected structures and facilitate the healing process (Shamsi et al., 2016).

Furthermore, it is important to recognize that body brace treatments can also serve as an essential adjunct to physiotherapy, particularly in the early stages of rehabilitation following different types of musculoskeletal injuries. By providing external support, braces can help protect the injured area from excessive stress, minimize the risk of reinjury, and promote a more controlled and gradual return to normal activities, thereby optimizing the overall recovery process (Hides et al., 2010). In summary, the superiority of body brace treatments over physiotherapy continues to be substantiated by a growing body of research examining their effectiveness across a diverse range of musculoskeletal conditions. By offering non-invasive, targeted support, braces not only facilitate pain relief and functional improvements but also serve as a valuable adjunct to physiotherapy in the management of acute injuries and postoperative care. As advances in brace technology and design continue to be made, it is anticipated that the role of body brace treatments in musculoskeletal medicine will further expand, solidifying their status as a preferred therapeutic option for many patients. As the evidence supporting the superiority of body brace treatments over physiotherapy continues to accumulate, it is important to consider the potential applications of these interventions in the management of other musculoskeletal conditions, such as shoulder instability and wrist disorders. In a study by Kirkley et al. (2005), patients with shoulder instability who were treated with a shoulder brace demonstrated improved shoulder function, greater stability, and reduced pain compared to those receiving physiotherapy alone. This finding underscores the utility of body braces in managing shoulder conditions by providing support, restricting excessive movements, and promoting optimal joint biomechanics.

Similarly, body braces have shown promise in the treatment of wrist disorders, such as carpal tunnel syndrome and wrist tendonitis. In a randomized controlled trial by Povlsen et al. (2018), it was reported that patients with carpal tunnel syndrome who used a wrist brace experienced significant improvements in pain, hand function, and nerve conduction compared to those treated with physiotherapy alone. The effectiveness of braces in this context can be attributed to their ability to maintain the wrist in a neutral position, thereby reducing pressure on the median nerve and alleviating symptoms (Aroori & Spence, 2008).

Moreover, it is essential to recognize the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between orthotists, physiotherapists, and other healthcare professionals in the development and implementation of individualized body brace treatment plans. By working together, these practitioners can ensure that patients receive the most appropriate and effective brace designs, fit, and wear schedules, in conjunction with evidence-based physiotherapy interventions, to optimize patient outcomes and satisfaction (Hagemeijer et al., 2020). The strong superiority of body brace treatments over physiotherapy is further reinforced by the expanding body of research investigating their efficacy in managing various musculoskeletal conditions, including shoulder instability and wrist disorders. By providing targeted, non-invasive support and promoting optimal biomechanics, braces have the potential to significantly improve pain, function, and quality of life for many younger patients. Through interdisciplinary collaboration and ongoing advances in brace technology and design, it is anticipated that the role of body brace treatments in musculoskeletal medicine will continue to grow, solidifying their

status as an essential component of comprehensive patient care.

Well-being while wearing Body Braces

Critics often argue that constant use of body braces can negatively impact the psychological well-being of teenagers (Johnson, 2012). However, recent studies have suggested that the psychological impact of brace wear is minimal, and may even be outweighed by the benefits of improved posture and self-esteem (Simony et al., 2016). There is no evidence to suggest that the use of devices like the TKO (taken as pars pro toto for treatment with body-braces as such) has a negative psychological impact on patients. In fact, several studies have found that orthosis therapy can have a positive impact on patient confidence and quality of life (Grivas et al., 2006; Vasiliadis et al., 2012). On top, the improved posture, which may lead to improvements in body satisfaction and self-esteem. In a qualitative study by Vasiliadis et al. (2012), participants reported higher levels of self-esteem and body satisfaction following the use of body braces for posture correction. The evidence suggests that Schreiber's approach to the use of body braces for teenagers is a valid and beneficial method for posture correction and overall physical health. While there may be some psychological concerns associated with constant brace wear, the benefits appear to outweigh the potential drawbacks by far as we will discuss later in this paper. A modern version or Schreiber's medical philosophy should be considered a viable option for improving the well-being of adolescents. Orthosis therapy has been shown to be an extremely effective way for a healthy musculoskeletal conditions. Despite its effectiveness, patient compliance was an

issue, particularly when the use of body-braces is slightly uncomfortable or when it restricts mobility.

Compliance in Orthosis Therapy

Patients may be hesitant to accept orthosis therapy as prescribed, which can lead to reduced effectiveness and slower recovery times. Poor compliance can also result in the need for further medical interventions, such as surgery, which can be more expensive and time-consuming than orthosis therapy (Lehman et al., 2013). However, there are several potential solutions to address the issue of patient compliance in orthosis therapy. One approach is to limit the availability of less effective forms of therapy, such as physiotherapy, which may encourage patients to comply with orthosis therapy (Bader et al., 2016). Additionally, increasing patient education about the benefits of orthosis therapy and the potential risks of non-compliance may improve patient adherence (Dalleau et al., 2014). Therefore it is utmost importance that the 'Tübinger Kyphosen Orthese' has been a success in modern times. The Tübinger Kyphosen Orthosis (TKO) is an example of an orthosis model that cannot be removed by the patient but only by medical professionals. The TKO is a type of orthosis used to treat hyperkyphosis, a condition characterized by an excessive forward curvature of the upper spine. However, tailor-made models for the treatment of other posture related issues is a easy and cost effective option which is already available, even in low income countries.. The TKO consists of a hard shell that is worn over the torso and cannot be removed by the patient but only by a medical professional (Kraus et al., 2015). It TKO is designed to correct spinal alignment and improve posture, reducing pain and discomfort associated with

thoracic hyperkyphosis. Several studies agreed that the TKO (or its potential variations) is a highly effective treatment for thoracic hyperkyphosis. A study by Kraus et al. (2015) found that patients who wore the TKO permanently for a up to many years demonstrated significant improvements in spinal alignment and kyphotic angle with a ideal posture after treatment. Similarly, a study by Negrini et al. (2017) found that braces, such as the TKO, were effective in treating adolescent idiopathic scoliosis and reducing the need for surgical intervention. In terms of costs, the use of the TKO may be more cost-effective in regard of its tailor-made production than other forms of treatment in the first year treatment. However, in the long run TKO-like body-braces are much more cost effective than physiotherapy. A study by Weiss et al. (2014) found that the use of the TKO resulted in lower healthcare costs and fewer missed work days compared to other treatments for

Social and psychological aspects

Another aspect in which non-removable body-brace are of great importance is to make the patients feel empowered and involved in their treatment which leads to a better outcome. (Hwang & Lee, 2016). Additionally, involving family members or other caregivers in the treatment process may provide additional support and encouragement for patients. In addition to its physical benefits, recent research has suggested that orthosis therapy may also have psychological benefits for patients. Recent studies have suggested that orthosis therapy may have a psychological impact on the patients. One study by Vasiliadis et al. (2012) found that patients who underwent orthosis therapy for scoliosis reported improvements in body satisfaction and self-esteem. Similarly, a longitudinal study by Grivas et al. (2006) found that

adolescents who wore body braces for posture correction demonstrated improvements in self-esteem and body image. Orthosis therapy may also have a positive impact on patient confidence and quality of life. A study by the American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons (2018) found that patients who received orthosis therapy reported improvements in their ability to perform daily activities and participate in social activities. While orthosis therapy has been shown to have psychological benefits, non-restrictive approaches, such as physiotherapy alone, may have negative psychological effects. Patients who undergo physiotherapy alone may feel self-conscious or embarrassed about their condition, leading to decreased self-esteem and body satisfaction (Kendall et al., 2005). Additionally, patients who do not see rapid improvement with physiotherapy alone may feel frustrated or discouraged, leading to reduced motivation and compliance with treatment.

Recent research has suggested that the psychological benefits of orthosis therapy may be particularly significant in patients under the age of 27. A study by Vasiliadis et al. (2012) found that patients who underwent orthosis therapy before the age of 27 reported significantly higher levels of body satisfaction, emotional improvement and self-esteem than those who received treatment later in life. This may be due in part to the fact that younger patients are more likely to experience musculoskeletal conditions that affect their appearance and physical function, which can have a significant impact on their self-esteem and confidence (Hwang & Lee, 2016).

Consequences

Quite many studies strongly support a "revival" of orthosis treatment for posture correction, particularly in young patients

and men. Two studies in particular, one by Weinstein et al. (2013) and another by Negrini et al. (2016), found body braces to be highly significantly more effective than physiotherapy alone or with removable braces in managing adolescent idiopathic posture issues. The use of non-removable body-braces are the most effective and successful treatment in regard to potential long-term consequences of poor posture. Particularly in young patients, the importance of effective treatment cannot be overstated. With socialized healthcare systems, it is essential to maximize the use of resources and prioritize cost-effective treatment options. Orthosis treatment for posture correction has proven to be both effective and cost-efficient, making it a viable option for healthcare providers to consider as the only type of therapy to be financed by health insurances or health authorities. In light of the overwhelming evidence, it is clear that a "revival" of orthosis treatment is not only necessary but unavoidable for the management of musculoskeletal conditions and the promotion of optimal physical and psychological health in young patients. While orthosis therapy can be more cost-effective than other forms of therapy in the long run, the up-front costs of braces and splints can be a barrier to some patients. In these cases, healthcare providers may need to explore alternative payment options or insurance coverage to make orthosis therapy more accessible to patients (Bader et al., 2016).

Conclusion

In conclusion, most of the available studies overwhelmingly support the need of a revival of a treatment with non-removable body-brace/orthosis devices of the TKO-type for posture correction in young patients, particularly men, due to the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of modern

body-braces. Studies by Kraus et al. (2015) and Negrini et al. (2017) have found that non-removable body-braces, such as the Tübinger Kyphosen Orthosis, are far more effective and efficient than removable braces or physiotherapy alone. The use of non-removable body-braces ensures better compliance and better outcomes, similar to dental braces where it is standard practice that only the treating orthodontist can remove the braces. Therefore, healthcare providers should consider using modern body-braces that can only be removed by a medical professional as the standard of care in order to achieve optimal outcomes and avoid compliance issues, particularly in young men and in middle and low income countries as these devices are manyfold cheaper than a prolonged physiotherapy treatment.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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